

Comparison of opioid consumption for postoperative analgesia in Mastectomy surgeries in Erector Spinae Block group and Non Erector Spinae Block group

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Abstract

Background: ESPB (Erector spinae plane block) has been used in multiple breast procedures, including mastectomies and breast reconstructions. However, its efficacy remains an unsolved debate. In light of these considerations, the purpose of this study was to ascertain the postoperative opioid use in the general anesthetic and ESP block groups.

Methods: This prospective comparative study was conducted among adult female patients undergoing mastectomy surgeries under general anaesthesia at Trichy SRM Medical College hospital & Research centre among 30 cases where 15 cases were included in group E (ESB group) and the rest 15 cases were included in group G (GA group). Data was entered in MS excel and analyzed using SPSS -20.

Results: In this study, both the group E and group G were similar in age and ASA classification without any statistical significant association. On assessing the post operative mean VAS score at 0 hr, 2 hrs, and 4 hrs, there were no significant difference noted between groups. However at 6 hrs and 12 hrs, mean VAS score in group E were remarkably lesser in group E compared to

group G. However, at 24 hrs both groups has similar in mean VAS score without any significant difference. Notably, requirement of rescue analgesia was high in group G compared to group E with significant difference. Additionally, mean time at need for first rescue analgesia was significantly longer in group E compared to group G. Mean nausea and vomiting score was significantly lesser in group E compared to group G, however mean patient's satisfaction score was similar in both the groups.

Conclusion: We conclude that ESP block was much efficacious in reducing pain and in turn favors with less consumption of analgesia and lesser incidence of nausea and vomiting among the cases undergoing mastectomy surgeries. Thus we strongly recommend the use of ESP block for cases undergoing mastectomy surgeries.

Key words: ESP block, mastectomy, General anesthesia

INTRODUCTION

Breast surgeries cover a broad range of operations, including reconstructive and oncologic mastectomy as well as breast augmentation. One thing they have in common is the severe pain that patients have after surgery; according to some studies, more than 50% of patients who have mastectomy and reconstruction suffer discomfort for up to a year after the procedure¹. While breast cancer treatments can be curative in most cases and greatly enhance quality of life, postoperative pain, both acute and chronic, can be extremely painful and impede functional abilities². Even though advancements in breast surgery research are continually yielding more aesthetically pleasing results with fewer complications, postoperative discomfort is still a problem for patients and a source of ongoing difficulty for surgeons³.

Opioid use for postoperative analgesia has increased dramatically during the last several decades. Addiction rates and opioid-related deaths have alarmingly risen to over 42,000 deaths per year in the US alone⁴. The opioid crisis has spurred ongoing efforts to enhance pain management during surgical operations, particularly breast surgery⁵. According to a case-control research including almost 500,000 surgical patients, patients having breast surgery are particularly vulnerable to acute and persistent postoperative pain⁶. The literature reveals that breast surgeons typically overprescribe opioids, even though many patients would rather tolerate their discomfort than take too many of them⁷. Therefore, in order to speed up patients' rehabilitation and combat the opioid crisis, it is the duty of the medical professional to look out benign pain management techniques.

Regional blocks have long been used as an adjunctive form of analgesia, but their acceptance as a postoperative pain management technique is relatively new⁸. ESPB is a cutting-edge method of regional anesthetic that was initially presented by Forero et al. as an effective interfascial block for thoracic neuropathic pain⁹. When given at T5, it showed the capacity to anesthetize unilateral multidermatomal feeling from T1 to L3 sufficiently¹⁰. Comparing ESPB to the frequently used PVB after thoracotomies, comparable pain reduction outcomes were observed with fewer side effects¹¹. ESPB has been used in multiple breast procedures, including mastectomies and breast reconstructions, throughout the last 24 months¹². In light of these considerations, the purpose of this study was to ascertain the postoperative opioid use in the general anesthetic and ESP block groups.

METHODS

This prospective comparative study was conducted among adult female patients undergoing mastectomy surgeries under general anaesthesia at Trichy SRM Medical College hospital & Research centre among 30 cases where 15 cases were included in group E (ESB group) and the rest 15 cases were included in group G (GA group). Cases between age 18-60 years from both genders and ASA class I and II were included in this study. Cases who were allergic to local anesthetic agents were excluded.

An earlier study by Swati et al¹⁰ has shown that the mean tramadol consumption among GA patients was 9.3(2.36)mg and 1.95(2.01)mg in ESPB group. Assuming similar observations will be made for the present study to deduct statistical significance at 5% level of significance with 90% power, the adequate sample size is 5 per group. However, considering the sub group analysis, it is proposed to take 15 per group. Therefore, a total of 30 patients were recruited and randomized into 1:1 ratio.

Patients underwent surgery under general anaesthesia. Post surgery, patients in the G group was extubated and transferred to PACU. In the E group, with the patient under general anaesthesia, patient were turned to lateral position, a single shot block with 20ml of 0.375% ropivacaine was given at the level of T5 vertebra after identifying the ipsilateral erector spinae muscle using USG and depositing the drug deep to it. The pain score was evaluated by means of visual analog score (VAS 0 - no pain; 10 - the worst pain imaginable) at the time of arrival in PACU and then after 2, 4, 6, 12, and 24 h after operation.

Postoperative analgesia is standardised with intravenous Paracetamol 15mg/ kg 6th hourly in both the groups. Rescue analgesia with intravenous Tramadol 50mg on demand or whenever VAS was ≥ 4 in both the groups. The number of patients requiring rescue analgesia and total tramadol consumption during the first 24 h after operation was recorded. The incidence and severity of nausea was assessed by four-point categorical scale (0 = none, 1 = mild, 2 = moderate, and 3 = severe) at three points of time 30 min, 1 h and 24 h postoperatively. Intravenous metoclopramide 10 mg will be given for severe nausea or vomiting. Patients' satisfaction with the technique was assessed at 24 h after operation by Likert scale (self-report

scale where 0 = strong dissatisfaction, 1 = dissatisfaction, 2 = neutral, 3 = satisfaction and 4 = strong satisfaction).

Data was entered in MS excel and analyzed using SPSS -20. Mann Whitney U test and Fishers chi square test were used appropriately. p value < 0.05 was considered significant.

RESULTS

In this study, both the group E and group G were similar in age and ASA classification without any statistical significant association.

Table 1: Clinical profile of study participants

Variables	Group E	Group G	p value
Age group			
31-40 years	1	1	0.5237
41-50 years	6	9	
51-60 years	8	5	
ASA class			
Class 1	6	7	0.8761
Class 2	9	8	

On assessing the post operative mean VAS score at 0 hr, 2 hrs, and 4 hrs, there were no significant difference noted between groups. However at 6 hrs and 12 hrs, mean VAS score in group E were remarkably lesser in group E compared to group G. However, at 24 hrs both groups has similar in mean VAS score without any significant difference.

Table 2: Comparison of mean VAS score between groups

Post operative pain -VAS score	Group E	Group G	p value
0 hr	2.4±0.2	2.5±0.3	0.8468
2 hr	2.7±0.3	2.8±0.6	0.7314
4 hr	2.9±0.4	3.1±0.4	0.3716
6 hr	3.0±0.5	3.6±0.4	0.0253*
12 hr	3.6±0.8	4.6±0.7	<0.0001*
24 hr	4.1±0.6	4.3±0.7	0.3457

*Significant

Notably, requirement of rescue analgesia was high in group G compared to group E with significant difference. Additionally, mean time at need for first rescue analgesia was significantly longer in group E compared to group G.

Table 3: Comparison of rescue analgesia between groups

Rescue analgesia	Group E	Group G	p value
Required	8	15	0.0315*
Not required	7	0	
Total	15	15	
Parameter	Group E	Group G	p value
Time at need for first rescue analgesia (hrs)	14.5±3.6	10.6±2.8	<0.0001*

*Significant

Mean nausea and vomiting score was significantly lesser in group E compared to group G, however mean patient's satisfaction score was similar in both the groups.

Table 4: Comparison of nausea and vomiting score and patient's satisfaction score between groups

Parameter	Group E	Group G	p value
Mean Nausea and vomiting score	1.3±0.3	2.1±0.5	<0.0001 *
Mean Patient's satisfaction score	3.2±0.4	3.0±0.5	0.735

*Significant

DISCUSSION

In patients receiving unilateral MRM, Bakeer A et al¹³. compared the analgesic effectiveness of PECS-II blocks and ultrasound guided ESP. They found that compared to the PECS group, a higher number of ESP participants needed rescue morphine analgesia. The ESP group consumed considerably more morphine overall and requested analgesia faster. One, two, and six hours following surgery, the ESP group experienced more intense pain. They asserted that the ESP block is less successful than PECS-II block in controlling postoperative pain following breast cancer surgery. Additionally, it lessens the requirement for morphine for the whole 24 hours following surgery and extends the duration of analgesia. The results of ESPBs were compared

with those of other regional blocks by Leong RW et al¹⁴. The analgesic efficacy of ESPB was shown to be similar to paravertebral block and inferior to pectoralis nerve block, according to a separate review of trials comparing it with these two procedures. In the group receiving paravertebral blocks, the incidence of pneumothorax was 2.6%; no problems pertaining to the other blocks were reported. This review has demonstrated that when compared to general anesthesia alone, the ESPB is more successful at lowering postoperative opioid consumption and pain scores up to 24 hours. Its effectiveness was comparable to that of paravertebral block, however it was not as effective as the pectoralis nerve block.

Abdella AM et al¹⁵ examined the benefits and downsides of varying LA volumes and ESPB concentrations on acute neuropathic pain following mastectomy, NK cell cytotoxicity, and the postoperative requirement for opioids and rescue analgesics. In comparison to the control group, both ESPB groups drank less morphine overall. As a postoperative rescue analgesic, ketorolac was less necessary in both ESPB groups than in the GA group. A comparable frequency of acute neuropathic pain following surgery was noted. The three groups under study did not differ in terms of NKC cytotoxicity; nevertheless, the postoperative cytotoxicity was higher than the preoperative one due to the high volume of LA. There have been no reported block problems, and ESPB groups have a lower incidence of PONV than the control group. They stated that when bupivacaine is given at a dose of 50 mg with varied volumes and concentrations, ESPB is a safe and effective analgesic modality that reduces the postoperative demand for opioids and rescue analgesics. Evaluation of the analgesic effects of ultrasound-guidance PVB and ESPB following breast surgery was the goal of Wittayapairoj A et al¹⁶. When comparing PVB to ESPB, the 24-hour morphine requirements were much lower in the former group. The PVB group also had lower total pain scores. While every patient in the ESPB group asked for more morphine, just 14 patients in the PVB group did so. In the PVB group, the dermatome of sensory blocking was more extensive. There were no significant complications in either group. They asserted that PVB offered broader sensory blocking following mastectomy, reduced pain scores, and a decreased need for postoperative opioids as compared to ESPB.

The effectiveness and safety of this block were evaluated by Sharma S et al¹⁷ in patients having axillary clearance and complete mastectomy. They found that the block group's 24-hour morphine use was 42% less than that of the control group. At 0, 1/2, 1, 2, 4, 6, 12, and 24 hours

after surgery, group B's postoperative pain score was lower than group C's. Within an hour after operation, 26 patients in group C and 14 in group B received rescue analgesia. The erector spinae block has the potential to be a dependable and safe method of analgesia during breast surgery. Thirty-two articles, including six randomized controlled trials, were considered in the review by ElHawary H et al¹⁸. ESPB showed better pain management and reduced opioid use as compared to tumescent anesthesia or no block. But when it came to managing pain, ESPB was less effective than pectoral nerve block. Patients who received ESPB as opposed to other pain management modalities reported reduced nausea and vomiting as well as higher levels of satisfaction overall. The administration of ESPB was found to be simple in the great majority of the investigations, and only one patient had a problem. They asserted that when utilized in conjunction with multimodal pain management for patients having breast surgery, ESPB is a potential kind of regional anesthesia that can reduce postoperative pain and the need for opioids. The analgesic efficacy of ultrasound-guided ESPB during breast cancer surgery was assessed by Gurkan Y et al¹⁹. They found that the ESP group's morphine intake dramatically dropped during postoperative hours 1, 6, 12, and 24. In comparison to the control group, the total amount of morphine used at 24 hours dropped by 65%. Regarding NRS scores, there was no statistically noteworthy difference between the groups. They demonstrated that patients having breast cancer surgery get a notable analgesic response from US-guided ESP block.

Altıparmak B et al²⁰ examined the effects of ESPB and ultrasound-guided modified pectoral nerve (PECS) block on patients undergoing unilateral MRM surgery's postoperative opioid consumption, pain scores, and intraoperative fentanyl demand. After radical mastectomy surgery, they found that modified PECS block was more successful than ESP block in reducing postoperative tramadol intake and pain scores. The effectiveness of ESPB and TPVB in managing acute pain following mastectomy was compared by El Ghamry MR et al²¹. The amount of morphine consumed during the first 24 hours after surgery and the time of the first analgesic request were found to be similar in both groups. There was no significant change in the intra-operative fentanyl intake. The VAS did not significantly differ between the two groups during the course of the 24-hour investigation. Pneumothorax occurred in four individuals in group I; there were no appreciable differences between the two groups. Vomiting and nausea rates were similar in the two groups. Every patient had a steady blood pressure pattern. Both TPVB and ESPB have demonstrated efficacy in managing pain following mastectomy and

minimizing the use of opioids during and after surgery. According to Altıparmak B et al²², group I's mean tramadol consumption at postoperative 24-hour mark was 149.52 mg, whereas group II's was 199.52 mg. When comparing the NRS scores of group I to group II, group I's scores were consistently lower. Both groups had comparable mean intraoperative fentanyl requirements. The higher dose of bupivacaine considerably decreased postoperative tramadol consumption following radical mastectomy surgery, even if ESP block given with each concentration of bupivacaine gave excellent postoperative analgesia.

According to Swisher MW et al²³, subjects with ESPBs consumed more opioids and had higher pain scores than PVBs. In neither group did any adverse events connected to blocks occur. They came to the conclusion that after non-mastectomy breast surgery, PVBs offered better analgesia and required less opioids. The postoperative analgesic efficacy of ESPB for MRM surgery was assessed by Singh S et al²⁴. According to their research, patients undergoing US-guided ESP block used considerably less morphine after surgery when compared to the control group. Only two patients in the US-guided ESP block group needed additional morphine after surgery, whereas all patients in the control group did. They asserted that effective postoperative analgesia might be achieved by administering US-guided ESP block before MRM surgery.

CONCLUSION

We infer that ESP block was much efficacious in reducing pain and in tern favors with less consumption of analgesia and lesser incidence of nausea and vomiting among the cases undergoing mastectomy surgeries. Thus we strongly recommend the use of ESP block for cases undergoing mastectomy surgeries.

Declarations

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Conflict of interest: None declared

Ethical approval: This study was registered with Institutional Human Ethical Committee.

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